

International Journal of Advances in Engineering & Scientific Research (IJAESR)

ISSN: 2349 -3607 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 -4824 (Print)

Available online at:

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-1-issue-4-aug-2014>

Email: editor@arseam.com

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OPPORTUNITIES FOR KITCHEN AND GARDEN WASTE BY UTILIZATION ECO-FRIENDLY ADDITIVES

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ABSTRACT

The focus of the research paper is to investigate the importance of biogas as an alternative energy sources. A survey was done to ascertain the amount of biogas that can be generated from various feed stock. A practical laboratory scale experimental design using kitchen and garden waste and effects of Alkaline [NaOH] on the volume of biogas generated. Results obtained revealed a high volume of gas generated when the operating conditions inside the digester is maintained at moderately alkaline condition. Further findings also reveal that the digester temperature remained within the range of 32°C to 35°C throughout the period of experimentation.

There was a digester tank of capacity 20 litre for decomposition of cow dung slurry and fruit waste. Two additives that are KOH and NaOH were used to make the buffer solution. Urea was added to increase the production of biogas. The fruit waste is grinded properly in so that the surface area of slurry is increased and material will easily decompose in short time.

This work can solve the problems of kitchen waste management as well as bring the fulfilment of energy requirement in terms of Biogas and optimization of biogas. The volume of the digester was 20 litres. The solid waste of 9kg was used which comprised of 5kg Cow dung, 2kg Fruit Waste, 2kg garden waste and 100 gm of KOH. The remaining space in the digester was filled with water. The parameters of total solid, Volatile solid, Non Volatile Solid at inlet and outlet slurry were calculated. The values obtained were 34.66, 77.23, and 22.77 in percentage.

Key Words: Biogas, KOH, NaOH, Eco-Friendly.

INTRODUCTION

A huge amount of solid waste is generated due to rapid industrialisation and population. In order to reduce the environmental conditions economically feasible measure are taken for solid waste management in rural and urban areas. A plan to turn solid organic waste that is kitchen waste and garden waste into efficient energy source through the process of anaerobic digestion was worked out. Biogas is produced from organic wastes by concerted action of various groups of anaerobic bacteria through anaerobic decomposition. Globally, the reduction of green house gas emissions particularly of CO₂ has become more important. Through the use of biogas plant, the CO₂ emission can be reduced in the atmosphere. It has been suggested the rate of production of biogas can be affected by use of additives and buffer solutions.

Biogas is the gas produced by the breakdown of organic matter through Anaerobic Digestion (AD). It is one of the renewable energy sources, such as solar energy and wind energy these sources are environmentally friendly. Solid waste may be classified as industrial waste, residential waste, construction waste, municipal solid waste, green waste and bio waste. If this waste is not recycled and disposed properly causes environmental hazards and diseases like typhoid, cholera, dengue, malaria etc. Thus the process of solid waste management is of vital importance in day to day life. This process includes collection, transportation, treatment and finally disposal of the solid waste.

In this study biogas was produced by using kitchen waste and garden waste. The kitchen waste comprised of unwanted fruits and vegetables whereas garden waste comprises of leaves, plants, shrubs, herbs and climbers. The quality of feedstock and nature of the sample affects the yield of gas. The feedstock should be mixed and grinded properly so that the volume of the surface area is increased and the gas is produced in short time period.

Biogas is produced in an oxygen free environment through anaerobic digestion. The process of anaerobic digestion occurs in following step that is hydrolysis, acidification, acetogenesis and methanogenesis. The content of biogas varies with the material being decomposed and the environmental conditions involved. The products in this reaction are methane, carbon dioxide, hydrogen sulphide and other organic gases in small amount. Potentially, all organic waste materials contain adequate quantities of the nutrients essential for the growth and metabolism of the anaerobic bacteria in biogas production. However, the chemical composition and biological availability of the nutrients contained in these materials vary with species, factors affecting growth and age of the animal or plant. Various wastes have been utilized for biogas production and they include amongst others; animal wastes, industrial wastes, food processing wastes, plant residues etc. These days poultry waste is highly used for the production of biogas since a huge amount of this waste is obtained in the society. Paper wastes are one of such wastes being considered as a potential feed stock. Waste papers are readily available from schools, offices, printing presses, factories etc, and in some developing countries are littered on the street as waste.

Materials and Methods

The laboratory simulated feedstock was a mixture of Kitchen Wastes (KW) and Garden Wastes (GW), the former was collected from the mess of Suresh Gyan Vihar University and the later from Jawahar Circle Garden, both the renowned places located in Jaipur city of Rajasthan. In order to

carry anaerobic digestion a digester of 20 litres capacity was used to design biogas plant..In which the bio mass waste substrates comprises of cow dung , raw food mess waste, garden waste, buffer materials and small quantity of additives were added . The digester tank will be filled with water and remaining space will be utilized for production of gas.

Methods

All experiments have been performed in 20L batch digesters essentially made of plastic. A set of 1 digester have been used at a time for experimentation. The following parameters of biogas production were calculated using various equipments.

- pH of the Sample
- Temperature
- Total solid
 - Total solid of inlet slurry.
 - Total solid of out let slurry.
- Non volatile solid
 - Non volatile solid of inlet slurry.
 - Non volatile solid of outlet slurry.
- Volume of gas

Equipments to be used:-

1. Water Tank
2. Pipe
3. T- Valve
4. gas Valve
5. Funnel
6. Tyre Tube

Work plan:-

The setup of the Biogas Plant was done in the Chemistry Lab of Gyan Vihar University, Jaipur. In this setup a digester tank of 20 litres was taken and was painted black in colour. If not painted the transparency of the tank leads to the penetration of sunlight which results into formation of algae. Thus as a result anaerobic digestion process is followed, i.e digestion occurs in an oxygen free environment. The organic matter disintegrates into smaller molecules and as a result of it a mixture of methane, carbon dioxide, hydrogen sulphide and other gases is produced.

For this process of biogas production the feed was prepared by using 5kg cow dung, 2kg Kitchen waste, 2kg Garden waste and 50 grams of Na_2CO_3 was used. The remaining space in the digester tank was filled with water. The feedstock was grinded properly so as to increase the surface area for potential yield of biogas in short time duration. The feedstock is fed into the digester tank with the help of funnel and is stored for 30 days. The parameters such as pH, temperature, volatile solid, total solid and non volatile solid were calculated and the analysis on the yield of biogas was done.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

It is observed that the yield of biogas is affected by adding 50 grams of Na_2CO_3 . After 30 days it showed that the rubber tube is filled with biogas and the gas burns with brown flame on ignition with KOH solution. The volume of the gas produced increases day by day and on 30th day it is observed to be 0.921 m³. Various parameters of inlet and outlet of slurry are as follows:-

Table 1: Variation of different parameter at inlet and outlet

Parameters	pH	Temperature	Total solid	Volatile solid	Non Volatile solid
Inlet	6.8	32°C	82.22%	74.67%	25.33%
Outlet	6.4	35° C	34.66%	77.23%	22.77%

Table 2: Experimental details/Observation

S.Nos.	Day	Sample appearance	Evolution of gas	Ignition of Gas	Smell	Volume of gas(in m ³)
1	1Day	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	It feels by hand that temperature of digester is rise	Ignition with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.482
2	5Day	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	It feels by hand that temperature of digester is rise	Ignition with blue flame	Smell is like CN	0.543

3	10day	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	It feels by hand that temperature of digester is rise	Ignition with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.642
4	15 Day	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	It feels by hand that temperature of digester is rise	Ignition with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.691
5	20 Day	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	It feels by hand that temperature of digester is rise	Ignition with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.755
6	25 Day	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	It feels by hand that temperature of digester is rise	Ignition with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.835
7	30 Day	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	Biogas is produced and observed Full gas container	Ignition with blue flame	Smell is like CNG	0.921

Figure: Volume of gas generated day by day

Fig: Volume of Gas (In m³)/ Days

Figure: **Volume of Gas (In m³) / Days**

Table: pH

Biogas Material in %

CONCLUSION AND SCOPE OF FUTURE WORK:-

The increase in solid waste management requires proper treatment and disposal in order to keep the environment green. This project concluded that the production of biogas lead to solid waste management by anaerobic decomposition of organic matter. This gas proves to be cheap and

inexhaustible. Feedstock is prepared by taking fixed proportion of garden waste and kitchen waste. The slurry is prepared by mixing the ingredients in fixed proportion with water. The physical and chemical parameter of inlet and outlet slurries from the samples was analyzed.

Calculation of the parameter of slurries reveals the high value of organic content which is easily decomposed by anaerobic bacteria and produced methane gas. Conversion of organic compound was done from higher molecular weight to lower molecular weight by the same bacteria. Generated Biogas during the digestion period was analyzed in terms of amount of biogas production as well as CH₄ and CO₂. To maintain the pH we can use additives like NaOH and Na₂CO₃. This additives and buffer material increase the yield of biogas. There is still more work to be done in near future, if the temperature and pH parameters can be control it can enhance the production of the Biogas with same quantity of the feed materials and further measurements can be carried out with different quantity of the feed slurries to check the amount and quality of the Biogas production at the time of digestion period.

In near future this work needs to be applied at larger scale so that it will bring financial benefits and eco-friendly environment. The biogas thus produced can be used for heating, cooking, power supply and the effluent can be used as rich nutrient fertilizer in farming. This kind of project may help us to build a safe and clean environment where fuel source can eco-friendly. And also increase the energy resources for the human beings. Thus this process of biogas production by the uses of unwanted solid waste should be promoted. This can be done by educating people and by imposing laws for proper treatment and disposal of the solid waste.

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